

Cuttlefish Ink Melanin Encapsulated in Nanolipid Bubbles and Applied through a Micro-Needling Procedure Easily Penetrates White Hair Facilitating Its Photoepilation

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ABSTRACT

Background: Photothermolysis of unwanted hair depends on the presence of melanin in the hair follicle as the chromophore, but is not effective in patients with non-pigmented, melanin-sparse hair shafts and follicles. This split-scalp, double-blind study was to monitor the efficacy of melanin bound in nanosomes to inject exogenous melanin into the hair follicles thus potentiating successful photothermolysis.

Material and Methods: Twelve patients, phototypes II-III, with white or very fair hair, were treated with a compound containing melanin encapsulated in nanosomes (Melaser[®]) together with a fluorescent marker. Two equal 6 cm² areas were marked on each side of the occiput of the subjects. The compound was applied to a randomly selected experimental side on each patient (area A), and a saline solution applied in the same manner to the contralateral control side (area B). Penetration of the melanin into the hair follicle was assessed using optical and fluorescence microscopy. Also, condition of hair structure was checked in vivo after standard laser settings used for epilation.

Results: A slight transient erythema was observed in those areas where the compound was applied with some perifollicular edema. No such effects were noticed in those areas where saline solution was applied. No persistent complications such as scarring, hypo- or hyperpigmentation were observed in any of the experimental or control areas. Under fluorescence microscopy, the hair structures in the areas to which the compound had been applied showed a clear melanin deposit confirmed by the immunofluorescence intensity, which was highest at 2 hours after application. By optical microscopy, external melanin was deposited in hair follicles. Tests with standard settings for epilation were efficacious in damaging melanin-marked white hair.

Conclusion: This study strongly suggests the safety and efficacy of the application of nanosomes encapsulating melanin for the introduction of melanin into hair follicles. Changes noticed in the hair structure compromising its viability indicated potential application of this external melanin marker for white hair photoepilation.

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INTRODUCTION

The reasons for the removal of unwanted hair can be divided into four main categories: hypertrichosis, hirsutism, aesthetic reasons, or after reconstructive surgical procedures, the last including the removal of hairs on flaps, grafts, or after transexual surgery.¹ Destroying hair follicles with lasers and other light sources has revolutionized the ability to eliminate unwanted hair. The following light sources have proven successful for a variety of skin types: ruby laser (694.3 nm), alexandrite laser (755 nm), diode laser (800-810 nm), neodymium:yttrium aluminium garnet (Nd:YAG) laser (1064 nm), and different IPL devices emitting

a broad spectrum from 550 to 1200 nm, depending on the cut-off filter.²⁻⁵

However, the endogenous chromophore melanin, which is the target for photoepilation, is not present in all types of hair. As a result, there is a lack of pigment in blond, gray, and white hair that led to the idea of external chromophore application.

Nanni et al. were the first to report on topically applied carbon particles suspended in mineral oil, which were massaged into the hair follicles followed by treatment with a

1064 nm Q-switched Nd:YAG laser.⁶ Although permanent hair removal was not achieved, the concept of exogenous chromophores was followed further. Based on the idea that externally applied melanin could be a potential chromophore, a topical spray containing liposomes encapsulating melanin was introduced to pigment the hair follicle.⁷ A report of successful dyeing of the hair follicle with liposomal melanin can be found.⁸ Although de Leeuw et al. indicate that 62.5% of their patients experienced hair reduction of 95% after 8 treatments with the combination of Liposome[®] and diode laser treatment,⁹ Sand et al. were not able to confirm their observations.¹⁰

Nanosomes offer benefits over liposomes with their much smaller diameter, and so, since 2010, we have been conducting a clinical study on a topical spray based on nanosomal-delivered melanin for non-pigmented hair photoepilation. In the present split-scalp, double blind study, we report on the first part of the series of studies to assess and confirm the localization and manifestation period of the encapsulated melanin, and to notice its potential application for laser epilation.

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SUBJECTS AND METHODS

Patients

The clinical study protocol was prepared, reviewed, and approved by the Antoni de Gimbernat Foundation Ethics Committee. Twelve patients with very fair or white hair were selected for the prospective study, 6 men and 6 women, ages ranging from 52 to 78 years, mean age of 69, and skin phototypes II and III on the Fitzpatrick scale. All patients were informed of the nature of the study and gave written informed consent for the whole of the treatment protocol, including consent for biopsies and photographs.

The Nanosomic Melanin Compound

The development of new liposomes has been constant,^{11,12} culminating in the availability of nanosomes, which are very small vesicles in the range of 50 to 200 nm in diameter. Nanosomes are made up of a bilayer of phospholipids that constitute a sphere where the active ingredients are confined. They obtain maximum diffusion of the active ingredients thanks to the efficacy of their transmembrane transport and their good bioavailability. The

active ingredient of the compound used in the present study was cuttlefish ink confined in nanosomes (Melaser[®], Laboratorios Sesderma, Valencia, Spain) with diameters from 80 to 120 nm. The melanin concentration was 0.52% with a pH of 8.5. The aim of nanosomal pigment delivery is to distribute a high concentration of melanin into the hair follicle in order to darken the hair shaft and root in order to facilitate elimination of the hair with light energy. In our studies, a solution of nanosomic melanin compound was prepared in a 50:50 proportion with fluorescein sodium salt 0.5 mg/ml (Sigma Aldrich, St. Louis, MO).

The nanosome envelope protects the encapsulated product from the action of enzymes and macrophages that alter and can destroy the phospholipid structure during its passage through the epidermis and dermis. The phospholipid nanoparticles that encapsulate the marker carry out a blocking action and enable multiple deposits in order to thoroughly cover the target with the fluorescein marker. The marker, as assessed with fluorescence, shows a high presence in hair and is soluble in water. It acts as a bio-agent and is similar to an exogenous melanin, but does not produce any undesired side effects.

Compound and Method of Application

To prepare the compound for application, 5 ml of the cuttlefish ink nanosomal suspension was mixed with an equal amount of 1 mg/ml fluorescein in suspension (50:50). Both suspensions were mixed using a spatula in a clean aluminium container. The product was stirred for 5 minutes keeping it well protected from the light, until a homogenous mixture was obtained.

Liposome-entrapped melanin was prepared to target hair follicles and hair shafts, although negligible amounts of delivered molecules may stay in the epidermis and dermis. The presence of small quantities of ink at these levels would not represent any risk of heating in the event of laser hair removal, as we have noticed in several trials, using lasers of various wavelengths and IPL systems in the previous phase of preparation of this prospective study.

Cuttlefish ink melanin UV-Vis absorption spectrum showed the typical absorption profile of eumelanin. Ultra violet light is strongly absorbed by melanin in particular at 335nm. Yellow and green light as well as near infrared light are also notably absorbed. The later penetrate deeper in dermis for absorption by hair structures leading to hair elimination.

In all 12 subjects, two 6 cm² areas equidistant from the centreline of the skull were selected on the lower occipital zone, shaved, and marked with a white cosmetic pencil. The nanosomic melanin compound was applied randomly to either the right or left side in each patient (experimental area A), and a saline solution was applied to the contralateral control area (area B, control) using the same protocol.

The areas were cleaned by rubbing with a cotton bud soaked in acetone. Before application of the compound or saline solution, homogeneous roller microneedling of the skin on both areas was achieved with a 192-needle roller, needle length 0.2 mm, to help the compound or saline penetrate through the epidermis. Bleeding was avoided so as not to produce oedema.

Microneedles rolled over the skin helped deliver cuttlefish ink melanin encapsulated in liposomes to white hair and other non-pigmented hair or laser resistant hair follicles. This process was the subject of investigation in this study as well as to check its efficacy in achieving damage to white hair after using the Alexandrite laser (Syneron-Candela, CA, USA), programmed with standard setting for epilation. The belief was that the process of introducing external melanin compound to the hair structure would facilitate photothermolysis and epilation, using laser and/or IPL systems.

The microneedle technique offers a minimally invasive and painless route for drug administration and is currently investigated by several research groups. Microneedles forms channels within a micron-sized dimension, thereby enabling delivery of a broad range of therapeutic molecules, including proteins, which would not otherwise cross intact skin.

Immediately after rolling, the compound with marker or the saline solution was then massaged in to the marked areas with a finger every 5 minutes for 1 hour so that it was completely absorbed by the skin. Once the application time was over, both areas under study were washed with soap and water and carefully rinsed. After the washing, 3 mm punch biopsies were taken, with the purpose of examining for fluorescence, at the intervals below from areas A and B, taking into consideration the direction of the hair growth so that both hair and follicle were included in the specimens.

Extra biopsy samples using the same punch diameter were also taken from all patients for examination with optical microscopy. Samples were prepared with Hematoxylin Eosin (HE/EO) and with Masson/Fontana staining. HE/EO staining was used for examining biopsies, which were taken before and immediately after treatment with the Alexandrite laser (using 18J/cm², 6mm beam diameter with adjacent pulses). The purpose was to examine the efficacy of the external pigment to facilitate laser epilation. The Masson/Fontana staining was used to specifically detect the external melanin used in this study and to follow its location in hair structure. Masson/Fontana staining samples were taken at all control points in which fluorescence examination of samples was carried out.

Collection and Preparation of Samples

Punch biopsies were taken bilaterally in all 12 patients enrolled in the study. Biopsies were taken and coded by a doctor blinded

as to which were the compound-treated and which were the saline-treated areas. Biopsies were taken 15 minutes after application of the compound with marker or the saline solution in four patients, 60 minutes after application in another four patients, and 2 hours after application in four more patients. Biopsies include samples for staining with Masson/Fontana, which were taken at all times of those samples for the fluorescence assessment. HE/EO stain samples were taken in all patients and from both areas of the split occipital zone. However, punch biopsies for HE/EO were taken only once after application of the cuttlefish melanin ink or saline serum application and immediately after laser pulses following epilation methodology. Epilation with laser was carried out on one of the edges, randomly chosen, of one of the occipital zones of the study.

"Microneedles rolled over the skin helped deliver cuttlefish ink melanin encapsulated in liposomes to white hair and other non-pigmented hair or laser resistant hair follicles."

For fluorescence assessment samples obtained were kept in the dark as much as possible for their microscopy examination. Specimens were processed as follows: biopsied tissue was set in 4% formaldehyde, maintained at 4°C for 24 hours in a dark container to minimize the loss of any fluorescence, and progressively embedded in optimal cutting temperature (OCT) compound at room temperature. First, the samples were placed in three parts saline solution and one part OCT. The samples were submerged in two parts saline solution and one part OCT 1 hour later and in one part saline solution and one part OCT, and finally, in undiluted OCT. Samples for study were preserved at -80°C. Thin (5 µm) slices were obtained using a Leica® cryostat. Specimens were washed in PBS to remove OCT and finally washed in distilled water.

Tissue slices were prepared with Masson/Fontana stain in order to check the location of melanin in white hair follicles and also to determine particularities of the external cuttlefish pigment. For staining, samples were first left for 1 hour in silver nitrate, and left for 24-48 hours in darkness at room temperature. They were then placed in chloride gold for 7 minutes, in 5% sodium thiosulfate 1-2 minutes, then washed in distilled water and treated with nuclear fast red for 4 minutes. After washing and dehydration, samples were mounted with DPX.

Three independent, expert pathologists familiar with immunohistochemistry, who were blinded as to whether the specimens came from compound-treated or saline-treated areas, carried out histological assessments. Evaluators used an

FIGURE 1. (A) GFP filtered fluorescent microscopy of skin samples after saline solution application (Control), or after application of a nanosomal melanin compound with 50:50 fluorescein at 15 minutes (B), 60 minutes (C), and 2 hours (D) post-application (10x). Figures 1 (E) – (H) show fluorescence microscopy under the same conditions as above but without the filter.

observational assessment method, scoring specimens from 0 to 8 (adapted from the Ashcroft scale for pulmonary fibrosis) to determine the amount of product present in the specimens corresponding to each of the time frames when the biopsies were taken.

A fluorescence microscope (Leica DM6000B) equipped with a digital camera (DFC480) and a Leica GFP filter, were used for the fluorescence assessment. Excitation of the sample was carried out with 470 ± 40 nm blue light. The fluorescent emission obtained was in the visible green waveband at 525 ± 50 nm. Assessment of the fluorescence intensity at the various time frames was determined by comparing images.

As for optical microscopic examination, a standard microscope was used at various magnifications and, in particular, to

examine results of laser pulses on white hair structure, marked with the external cuttlefish melanin pigment.

RESULTS

Side Effects

Slight erythema was noted in those areas where the compound and marker were applied, and no adverse effects were noticed in those areas where saline solution was applied. No persistent complications such as scarring, hypo-, or hyperpigmentation were observed in any of the treated areas, whether treated with the compound or just the saline solution.

Evaluation of Samples

Optical microscopy

Histologic evaluation of hair follicles with Masson Fontana staining after topical application of the nanosomal melanin

FIGURE 2. Masson Fontana stain of skin samples. (A) and (E) representing saline treatment (controls). (B), (C), and (D) are shown at 15 minutes, 60 minutes, and 2 hours after application of a nanosomal melanin compound with 50:50 fluorescein (X 250). (F), (G), and (H) are at the same time frames as (B) – (D) but at a lower magnification (X 125). Note the presence of a clear deposit of melanin both in the follicle and inside the hair in the compound-treated specimens

showed impregnation in the hair follicle, whereas such findings were not seen in the area that was pretreated with saline solution (Figure 1). The melanin impregnation could be quantified in comparison to the controls and the samples taken at the different time points. Fifteen minutes after applying the compound, images were obtained that clearly outlined the anatomical structure of the hair (Figure 1).

Masson Fontana staining permitted estimation of the presence of the cuttlefish melanin compound on hairs (Figure 2). Samples showed that the nanosomal melanin had reached the follicular canals 15 minutes after the skin microneedle rolling (Figure 2) and continued to penetrate during the massage procedure.

Samples stained with HE/EO taken immediately after laser pulses for epilation showed, in all cases, changes in hair follicle architecture compatible with compromising hair viability. Haemorrhage phenomenon was present with blood extravasations mostly located at the infundibulum level, which presented signs of damage and separation of sheets. There were slight, limited signs of perifollicular coagulation, but the dermis was

of standard characteristics with no noticeable changes or signs of burning in any of all the samples examined (Figure 3-4)

Fluorescence Microscopy

The intensity of the fluorescence and melanin staining was slightly higher when the samples taken at 60 minutes after application of the compound were observed, but fluorescence was most clearly visible in transverse hair sections from the two-hour biopsies, showing that most of the delivered melanin-producing fluorescence reaction was concentrated on the infundibulum and follicle. Fluorescence was in fact significantly apparent within the hair structures over the time course of the experiment as a result of the gradual penetration of the nanosomal melanin into the body of the hair (Figure 1). The epidermis demonstrated a mild fluorescence, which can be attributed to the cleansing of the skin prior to taking of the biopsies. No fluorescence, other than normal basal skin fluorescence, was observed in the control group in any of the samples (Figure 1).

The 3 independent evaluators scored the degree of fluorescence based on the fluorescent microscopy images using the adapted

FIGURE 3. Skin x 250 HE/EO. (A) Sample with fluorescein immediately after laser pulses. No epidermal or dermal alterations. Some inflammatory infiltration is noticed. (B) saline serum control sample immediately after laser pulses. No epidermal or dermal alterations.

FIGURE 4. Skin x 400 HE/EO. Saline serum control sample immediately after laser pulses. (A,B) Transversal cutting of the hair follicles showing no alterations.

Ashcroft scoring method, the intensity of the fluorescence corresponding to the amount of melanin deposited in the follicle by the nanosomal delivery method (Figure 5). All three evaluators observed that the extent of the pigment deposition was directly related with time. In other words, the values of pigment deposition obtained from the evaluators' assessments could be correlated with the times when the biopsies were taken.

DISCUSSION

In this prospective controlled study, 12 patients with phototypes II-III, were randomly treated on the occipital area with nanosomes containing melanin, and saline on the contralateral side. Mild and transient sequelae (erythema and oedema)

were observed in 20% of those areas where compound had been applied, but no persistent pigmentary changes or scarring were observed in any treated area. Histological evaluation with Masson Fontana staining confirmed gradual and selective impregnation of the hair follicle with the liposomal melanin pigment, which was quantitatively confirmed with fluorescent microscopy.

In control samples, fluorescence detected in the dermis corresponded to skin basal auto-fluorescence. During examination of tissue samples, we were able to notice clear differences in concentration of fluorescence-pigment between samples marked with fluorescent cuttlefish ink and those that served

FIGURE 5. Skin x 250 HE/EO (A) Saline serum control sample (before). Various cutaneous layers appear normal. (B) Fluorescein sample (before). Various cutaneous layers appear normal.

as control. In control samples in which a saline serum was applied, no fluorescence was observed, except for the normal tissue auto fluorescence.

As for samples stained with HE/EO, examination demonstrated the changes observed after laser treatment of areas in which Melaser[®] was used, the follicle and hair suffered structural changes, similar to those observed when photoepilation is carried out on dark hair. These changes demonstrate that the external pigment of the cuttlefish ink located in white hair makes it possible to practice efficacious epilation of white hair. Moreover, tissue samples taken from areas in which saline serum was rubbed on the skin that also received laser treatment did not show any tissue alteration but inflammatory infiltration with no damage to hair follicle or its vital condition.

The success of lasers and IPL systems for epilation, under normal conditions, is directly related to the content of melanin as the endogenous chromophore.¹³ In pigmented hairs, during the anagen phase, not only do the hairs grow but there is also an increasing correlation with the melanin in the cells of the

follicular matrix, the sheath, and the hair bulge. This phase is considered to be the most optimum for photoepilation and hair elimination. In the transition and resting phases, catagen and telogen respectively, melanin decreases until it disappears and the hair falls out. In white, grey, blonde, or fine hair, there is a lack of melanin. This explains the often-poor outcomes of laser photoepilation in non-pigmented-hairs.

The idea of selectively dyeing blond, white, and gray hair follicles might be an excellent approach for permanent laser hair removal. Clinical studies have shown that active ingredients applied in the conventional way on the skin remain in most instances in the epidermis. Only a few active substances penetrate the epidermis and go into the dermis, where they can exert their desired action of coloring the hair structures which are deeply located in the dermis. This difficulty for most substances to penetrate the skin and restrict transdermal delivery is related with the barrier function of the stratum corneum, the outermost layer of the skin. The stratum corneum ranges from 10 to 20 μm in thickness and consists of highly differentiated keratinocytes (corneocytes) embedded in an intercellular lipid matrix of mainly fatty acids, ceramides,

FIGURE 6. Skin x 400 HE/EO. (A) Saline serum control sample (before) shows normal conformation of the transversal cutting of the hair follicle. (B) Fluorescein sample (before) shows normal conformation of the transversal cutting of the hair follicle..

cholesterol, and cholesterol sulfate. To penetrate into the skin, drug molecules must be small in size and/or low molecular weight. Lipophilic molecules can penetrate the skin deeper than hydrophilic ones. In addition melanin has a very poor solubility, is soluble in water and not soluble in organic solvents, making it difficult to bypass the natural skin barrier. Moreover, melanin is generally believed to have a high molecular weight, so it is not possible that it can penetrate to target hair structures. Therefore, encapsulation of natural melanin (cuttlefish ink melanin) in liposomes and repetitive external application and massaging after microneedle rolling allows an effective coloring of hair. Encapsulation in liposomes of melanin enhances its transdermal penetration; in this sense, melanin liposomal lotions have been employed in the last years but with conflicting results: In a clinical study Sand M, et al, in 2007¹⁰ conducted in 16 patients with blond, gray or white hair, a melanin liposomal spray was applied on the treatment sites 12 times a day (6 times in the morning and 6 times in the evening), for a period of 8 weeks before each laser treatment. Patients were advised to shave the areas 2 days

before treatment and stop applying the liposomal melanin the night before treatment. The clinical outcome was disappointing, because of the weakness of hair reduction and high costs of the procedure. In the Leeuw study,⁹ 40 individuals with white, grey or blonde hair were also instructed to apply a melanin liposomal spray 6 to 8 times a day, 14 days prior to the treatment. But, in both trials, the application mode had several inconveniences, eg., melanin was required in large amounts and it needed application several times a day for several weeks, with the additional inconvenience that home applications lacked control and patient compliance. In any case, some patients showing good results at the beginning of treatment but when application of the lotion was reduced it lead to negative results.

Various techniques have been proposed to enhance penetration of active ingredients into deeper skin structures. Electroporation, sonophoresis, and iontophoresis are a few of them and recently, skin needling has been described as a technique able to increase transdermal drug absorption. Microneedle

FIGURE 7. Skin x 250 HE/EO. Folliclum transversal cut. Sample with fluorescein immediately after laser pulses. (A) Damage to the infundibulum is noticed. (B) Some micro-haemorrhage is observed. (C) Loss in hair shaft architecture with detachment of its layers. Minor alterations with coagulation-like phenomenon in adjacent dermis is seen.

technique overcomes the stratum corneum barrier and offers a minimally invasive and painless route of administration. Dermaroller® (Dermaroller GmbH, Voltenbuettel, Germany) is one of these devices. DermaRoller®, a commercially available handheld device, has metal microneedles of 0,2 mm, which produce microporation. Once needles are rolled on the skin, they puncture the outer skin layer barrier. Henry S et al., in 1998 first reported the use of microneedles to enhance drug delivery across the skin, showing that the primary barrier to active transport was located in the upper 10-15 micron of the

skin. Microneedling is a superficial painless procedure because nerves are found deeper in tissue. Manufacturing of arrays of microneedles should be long enough (0,2 mm) to cross the superficial skin barrier but not extra long that they stimulate nerves, or produce bleeding. When no pain is caused, permeability of skin in vitro is increased, for example, for calcein when used as a drug model by up to 4 orders of magnitude.

Rollers are available in varying microneedle lengths (ranging from 0.13 to 2.5 mm), each specific needle length depends on

the nature of treatment it is employed for. Recent studies with different types and lengths of microneedles have helped in proposing an ideal range of microneedle lengths for optimal, painless drug delivery. Henry et al. had reported an increase in human skin permeability up to a magnitude of 4 orders with the use of 150 μm long needles, which is on the lower side of their length scale. Microneedle lengths up to 750 μm are reported to be painless when rolled over the skin.

In summary, an early report using external melanin to help eliminate white, grey, and blonde hair published by Nanni et al. in 1997⁶ was not optimal in the results. The study protocol included applications of the melanin, 6 to 8 times a day over 14 days, which could be judged long and tedious, although good results were reported after 10 treatment sessions. Moreover, these results were not confirmed in a double blinded study that was later carried out with more or less the same protocol,⁷ applying the melanin in liposomes over 8 weeks before the treatment, 12 times a day. Cuttlefish ink melanin is easily introduced by the punctures produced by the roller device with the 0.2 mm micro needles. The melanin liposomal solution is applied once the roller is rolled over and the needles penetrate the stratum corneum, opening up fine channels through which the melanin passes the epidermis down to the hair follicle. The cuttlefish ink melanin located in the hair follicle becomes the chromophore for selective photothermolysis of non-pigmented hair.

Channels formed remain open for a few minutes, therefore additional melanin penetrates to the hair structure by massaging and softly rubbing the product on the skin. This maneuver drastically reduces the time required for introducing the product to the hair follicle, when compared to time required in previously mentioned reports. Also, the amount of product needed is considerably reduced, since penetration shows high effectiveness, as demonstrated in our study.

Compared to previous studies using liposomes, the nanosomal technology used in the current study has the following advantages: (i) the size of the nanosomes is between 80-120 nm in diameter; (ii) the melanin concentration is very high, which contributes to targeting the hair follicle very easily; and (iii) The coupled fluorescence made it possible to follow the kinetics of melanin impregnation via the nanosomal encapsulation. The data based on these diffusion kinetics is essential because they could help to decide when a significant amount of encapsulated melanin pigment would have reached and impregnated the hair follicle and root, thereby allowing the performance of an effective photoepilation procedure in white, fair, or grey hair with little or no endogenous pigmentation.

We should note that the study has some shortcomings in methodology: (i) The small number of patients did not allow a high level of statistical analysis. However, the submission of

FIGURE 8. Graph showing staining of the follicular duct over time. The staining intensities of the product were scored and summed to obtain a combined score on a scale from 0 (non-exposed hair follicle) to 8 (total pigmented hair follicle) based on an adapted Ashcroft scale.

the project to an ethics committee required a protocol involving a limited number of patients to demonstrate the lack of major side effects and the pharmacokinetics of this therapy. After these initial positive results, we are in the process of clinically testing the effectiveness of photoepilation with this product in a prospectively large patient sample in various medical centers. (ii) A true control group is lacking, but the fact that there was a split contralateral study in the same individuals enhanced the power of the observations. It would also be helpful to compare this technique to electrocoagulation with combined radiofrequency and laser,¹⁴ or other methods. (iii) As underlined by Sand et al.,¹⁰ There are cost considerations to be taken into account to allow commercial production of a reasonably-priced and easily-handled version of the compound. However, the potential extensive use of such a product, given the changes in hair colour associated with the greying of the population and the fairly large percentage of ethnically fair-haired populations, mass production of the compound will help to reduce its cost.

CONCLUSION

This study underlines the efficacy and safety of nanosomes encapsulating melanin to target melanin into the hair follicle in hair with little or no endogenous pigmentation. Future clinical studies will hopefully confirm the efficacy of this therapeutic approach for successful photoepilation of white hairs.

DISCLOSURES

Dr. Gabriel Serrano is the Medical Director of SeSDerma Laboratories, Valencia, Spain. Dr. Inmaculada Expósito works for Research and Development Laboratories, SeSDerma Laboratories, Valencia, Spain. None of the other authors have conflicts of interests to declare.

REFERENCES

1. Nouri K, Vejjabhinanta V, Patel SS, Singh A. Photoepilation: a growing trend in laser-assisted cosmetic dermatology. *J Cosmet Dermatol*. 2008; 7(1):61-7.
2. Gansel RW. Photoepilation: state-of-the-art. *Hautarzt*. 2008; 59(2):124-30.
3. Drosner M, Adatto M. Photo-epilation: guidelines for care from the European Society for Laser Dermatology (ESLD). *J Cosmet Laser Thera*. 2005; 7(1):33-8.
4. Nanni CA, Alster TS. Laser-assisted hair removal: side effects of Q-switched Nd:YAG, long-pulsed ruby, and alexandrite lasers. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 1999; 41(2 Pt 1):165-71.
5. Nanni CA, Alster TS. Long-pulsed alexandrite laser-assisted hair removal at 5, 10, and 20 millisecond pulse durations. *Lasers Surg Med*. 1999; 24(5):332-7.
6. Nanni CA, Alster TS. Optimizing treatment parameters for hair removal using a topical carbon-based solution and 1064-nm Q-switched neodymium:YAG laser energy. *Arch Dermatol*. 1997; 133(12):1546-9.
7. De Leeuw J, de Vijlder HC, Bjerring P, Neumann HA. Liposomes in dermatology today. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2009; 23(5):505-16.
8. Trelles MA. In Camacho F. ed. *Monografías Dermatológicas*. Ed. Aula Médica, Madrid, 2013.
9. De Leeuw J, Van der Beek N, Neugebauer D. Permanent hairremoval of white, gray and light blond hair after laser treatment combined with melanin encapsulated liposomes. URL: www.liposome.net.
10. Sand M, Bechara FG, Sand D, Altmeyer P, Hoffmann K. A randomized, controlled, double-blind study evaluating melanin-encapsulated liposomes as a chromophore for laser hair removal of blond, white, and gray hair. *Ann Plast Surg*. 2007; 58(5):551-4.
11. Jung S, Otberg N, Thiede G, Richter H, Sterry W, Panzner S, Lademann J. Innovative liposomes as a transfollicular drug delivery system: penetration into porcine hair follicles. *J Invest Dermatol*. 2006; 126(8):1728-32.
12. Li L, Hoffman RM. Topical liposome delivery of molecules to hair follicles in mice. *J Dermatol Sci*. 1997; 14(2):101-8.
13. Aljjanpoor R, BejehMir AP, Mokmeli S. Successful white hair removal with combined coloring and intense pulsed light (IPL): a randomized clinical trial. *Photomed Laser Surg*. 2011; 29(11):773-9.
14. Sadick NS, Laughlin SA. Effective epilation of white and blond hair using combined radiofrequency and optical energy. *J Cosmet Laser Ther*. 2004; 6(1):27-31.

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